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THE CAUSES AND EFFECTS OF YOUTH RESTIVENESS, TERRORISM AND MILITANCY IN THE NIGER DELTA REGION OF NIGERIA AS PERCEIVED BY THE NIGER DELTA UNIVERSITY, BAYELSA STATE'S UNDERGRADUATES: IMPLICATION FOR COUNSELLING

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Abstract

The focus of this research paper is on the causes and effects of Youth Restiveness and Militancy in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria, as perceived by the Niger Delta University undergraduates in Bayelsa State of Nigeria: Implication for counselling. The design adopted for the study is the descriptive survey design. One thousand Six hundred and ninety (1690) undergraduate students of Niger Delta University formed the population of the study. While the sample size comprised 338 undergraduates selected through random sampling technique from the education faculty of the university. The researchers developed the Youth Restiveness and Militancy (YRM) Questionnaire with 21 items and used it for the study. Three research questions and two hypotheses were formulated for this study. For the two hypotheses, there were no significant differences on the basis of gender in the perceived factors responsible for youth restiveness and militancy in the Niger Delta Region and the perceived causes of youth restiveness and militancy on religion issues. The major issues shown on the results include slow or casual approach of government, corruption, unemployment, poverty and bad governance which are causal issues of the cankerworms. Furthermore, from the results, there were evidence that youth restiveness and militancy may culminate in economic stagnation, fear and suspicions, political instability, terrorism, et-cetera. Remediations to the canker worms include creation of employment for the youths, provision of counselling services in schools and communities, poverty eradication by government and so on. The following recommendations were made as fallouts from the study which included peace education at all levels of education, job creation for all youths and the provision of counselling services in the universities, secondary schools and the communities.

Keywords: Youth Restiveness; Terrorism; Militancy; Niger Delta.

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1. Introduction

As one of the biggest countries in Africa with a near one hundred and eighty million people, Nigeria is expected to experience many political, social, religious and cultural problems. Some of such problems the country has been contending with over the years include drug abuse, robbery, security challenges such as terrorism in the north east and elsewhere. Oyadeyi (2012) opined that the country is passing through a global economic depression, decay in critical sectors of socio-economic life, corruption, poverty, unemployment and reduced life expectancy unchecked everywhere. According to the above author, while these avalanches of challenges are starring the country, another dimension, youth restiveness and militancy evolved in different parts of the country, especially, in the Niger Delta regions. He further asserted that this newer developments have brought breakdown of law and order, destruction of property, attack on constituted authority and the killing of innocent citizens of Nigeria. Youth restiveness and militancy have taken different dimension often leading to killing and wanton destruction of properties especially in the oil-rich Niger Delta regions where oil-pipelines are carelessly broken. Killing of innocent ones always go with such attacks and plundering.

As great security risks to this country, social restiveness, terrorism and militancy causes killings, destruction of public properties, confusion, rioting, hostage taking, arson, extortion of money from innocent citizens, robbery, looting, et-cetera. Those found perpetuating these acts include the unemployed, students, dropouts and university undergraduates/graduates from tertiary institutions. Findings have shown, severally, that these hoodlums are hired by tribalised leaders, politicians or religious extremists to perpetuate these bloody acts for peanut.

Enueme and Onyeme (2010) opined that Nigerian youths have for some years developed into what could be regarded as social loafing, non-conformity behaviour, illusions of self and group vulnerability. Restiveness means refusal to be controlled, especially the adolescents in our society. Such actions are geared up with the insatiability of our youths by government or people in authorities (Oyadeyi, 2012). Enueme and Onyeme (2010) have equally observed in their study that very many youths all over the world, especially Nigeria have become non-conforming to regulations and rules from higher authorities, possibly because of societal sophistications, corruptions, youthful exuberances, identity formation, home/school context inducement, et-cetera. When youths take to unwholesome behaviours generally in a community, it is tagged restiveness. Such behaviours in most cases lead to breakdown of law and order, disruption of activities of production, ethnic hostilities, and destruction of public and government properties. In other words, youth restiveness is a sustained protest to enforce desired outcome from constituted authority characterized by violence and disruption of lawful activities (Elegbeleye, 2005).

To be candid, in Nigeria, it is becoming fashionable to use restiveness, terrorism or militancy as a transactional device to get what they desired from concerned authorities or the government (Enueme and Onyeme, 2010). Historically, the origin of these nefarious acts by these young ones date back to the 1930s. In Nigeria, these villainous activities were first noticed in the days of Herbert Macaulay in 1934, when he set up a political party without the consent of the educated youths. This gave rise to the formation of political parties like the NCNC (1945), NPC (1949) and the AG (1951). Each of these parties had their powerful youth wings.

After these era, it became a normal vogue that higher institutions started forming students union governments. It now moved like a prairie fire when campus cultism, gangsterism, ethnic cliques, and others came on board with the same or similar motives. There were other non-campus cliques that were ethnologically militants. Such groups include movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Odua People's Congress (OPC), Arewa Consultative Forum (ACF), Movement for the Actualisation of the Sovereign States of Biafra (MASSOB) which is today the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), Movement for the Survival of Ogoni People (MOSOP), et-cetera. The Major causes for the formation of these pressure groups include bad governance, poverty, unemployment, marginalization, ignorance, youthful exuberance, corruption in high places, et-cetera, in the country (Chukwuemeka, 2010 and Oyadeyi, 2012).

Oyadeyi (2012) opined that other major causes of restiveness, militancy and terrorism include religious intolerance, buying of votes/election rigging, tribalism and corruption in high places. Again, lack of social welfarism, corruption, misinformation, lack of humanitarian activities and poverty precipitate the trio youthful dangers in our society. These various groups mentioned above are highly obnoxious mostly with or without agenda and or agitations. Infact, because of their facelessness, societal evil men, ethnic groups and or politicians hire them for their selfish aims and agenda to unleash mayhem in society in form of terrorism, militancy, kidnapping, killing during elections, robbery, maiming and ritual killings. Therefore, to curb and or ameliorate the excesses of youth restiveness, terrorism and militancy in Nigeria and elsewhere in the world, this research work is tailored in such a way that the youths perceptions on the causes, effects and remedies of these evils are known.

Purposes of the Study

The followings are the specific purposes of this study:

- 1) To find out the factors responsible for youth restiveness, terrorism and militancy in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.
- 2) To find out the perceived effects of youths restiveness, terrorism and militancy in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.
- 3) To find out the techniques for curbing or ameliorating youth restiveness, terrorism and militancy in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

Research Questions

- 1) What are the factors responsible for youth restiveness, terrorism and militancy in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria?
- 2) What are the perceived effects of youth restiveness, terrorism and militancy in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria?
- 3) How can Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy be curbed or ameliorated in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria?

Null Hypotheses

- 1) There is no significant difference in the perceived causes of youth restiveness, terrorism and militancy on the basis of gender in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.
- 2) There is no significant difference in the perceived causes of youth restiveness, terrorism and militancy on the basis of religion in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

2. Materials and Methods

The descriptive survey design was adopted in this research work. One thousand six hundred and ninety (1690) undergraduate students of Niger Delta University formed the population of the study. Through random sampling technique a sample size of 338 undergraduates were selected from the faculty of education using the department of educational foundations (Guidance and Counselling option). The 200 and 300 level students of guidance and counselling unit formed the participants of the control and treatment groups of the study. These participants were drawn from the political science and Arts students of the counselling option of the department.

The questionnaire used for the study was titled "Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy (YRTM)" for collection of data. Experienced experts from the department scrutinized this instrument and needed inputs and corrections were made to ensure face and content validity in the scale. The yielded reliability of the instrument was 0.78 after the test-retest methodology of the scale. There were two main sections in the instrument. The section A part of the instrument treated the personal data of the participants. But the Section B which had three sub-divisions had sub-section 1 (factors responsible for youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy). Sub-section 2 had 10 items on effects of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy. While sub-section 3 of 17 items had information on strategies for curbing/ameliorating Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria. The researchers administered the instrument with the assistance of some staff of the guidance and counselling unit in the department. To analyze the collected data, the statistics of frequency counts, simple percentages and Z-test were used.

Research Question 1: What are the factors responsible for youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria?

Table 1: Frequency count and percentages of perceived factors responsible for Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria

S/N	Factors Responsible for Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria	Yes	%	No	%	Undecided	%
1	Lack of family and community counselling in the country	222	65.7	66	19.5	50	14.8
2	Slow/causal approach of government to sensitive issues	276	81.7	30	8.9	32	9.5
3	Corruption	310	91.7	12	3.6	16	4.7
4	Poverty is a major cause of Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy	310	91.7	28	8.3	0	0.0
5	Tribal and sectional loyalty among citizens	230	68.1	70	20.7	38	11.2
6	Get rich quick syndrome	248	73.4	56	16.6	34	10.01
7	Inadequate educational opportunities and resources	244	72.2	42	12.4	52	15.4
8	Unemployment	316	93.5	16	4.7	6	1.8
9	Marginalization and underdevelopment of some area/sections	258	76.3	44	13.0	36	10.7

10	Social inequality	252	74.6	48	14.2	38	11.2
11	Inadequate attention to environmental degradation in oil producing communities	246	72.8	52	15.4	40	11.8
12	Inadequate counselling services for citizens in schools	236	69.8	66	19.5	36	10.7
13	Lopsidedness in the sharing and allocation of national resource	216	63.9	82	24.3	40	11.8
14	Youthful exuberance 216	216	63.9	66	19.5	56	16.6
15	Religious intolerance	252	74.6	54	16.0	32	9.5
16	Ignorance on the part of citizens	248	73.4	58	16.0	32	9.5
17	Inadequate civic and moral instructions in school	230	68.1	64	18.9	44	13.2
18	Denial of justice	248	73.4	50	14.8	40	11.8
19	Social inequality	252	74.6	48	14.2	38	11.2
20	Election rigging	260	76.9	42	12.4	36	10.7
21	Imbalance reporting by mass media	168	49.7	96	28.4	74	22.0

From table 1, the results show that all the perceived factors are truly responsible causes of youth restiveness, terrorism and militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria. The items are 8, 3, 19, and 2 in chronological order are the major causes of youthful restiveness, terrorism and militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria. These are unemployment (93.5%), poverty and corruption (91.7%), and bad governance (81.7%). However, the least of these factors is imbalance reporting by mass media (49.7%).

Research Question 2: What are the perceived effects of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria?

Table 2: Frequency counts and percentages of perceived effects of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria.

S/N	Item	Yes	%	No	%	Undecided	%
1	It may bring the nation's economy to a standstill	298	88.1	10	3.0	30	8.9
2	Relocation of citizens of their ethnic/tribal localities	270	79.9	32	9.5	36	10.7
3	Exodus of foreigners from the country	262	77.5	28	8.3	48	14.2
4	Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy may lead to break up of the country	284	84	28	8.3	26	7.7
5	Civil war	282	83.4	20	5.9	36	10.7
6	People may live in fear and suspicion	314	93	14	4.1	10	3.0
7	Political instability	290	85.8	18	5.3	32	9.5
8	Psychological/emotional torture of victims and relatives	284	84	22	6.5	32	9.5
9	Collapse/closure of industries/companies	292	86.4	14	4.0	32	9.5
10	Education backwardness	264	78.1	26	7.7	48	14.2

The table 2 reveals the various frequency counts and percentages of the perceived effects of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria. It equally shows the consequences that follow. It is crystal clear that all the responses show that these trio evils spell doom for the country. The highest was item 6 (314 with 93%), while the lowest was item 3 (262 with 77.5%).

Research Question 3: How can Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy be curbed or ameliorated in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria?

Table 3: Frequency counts and percentages of perceived techniques for curbing or ameliorating Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria?

S/N	Item	Yes	%	No	%	Undecided	%
1	Transparent leadership and governance	298	88.2	24	7.1	16	4.7
2	Enlightenment on peace building should be embarked upon by government, counsellors, religious organisations and NGOS	280	82.8	42	12.4	16	4.7
3	Counselling Nigerians to be positive and rational in their thinking can help in reducing restiveness, terrorism and militancy	304	89.9	12	3.6	22	6.5
4	Aggressive poverty eradication drive and creation of employment opportunities for the youths	286	84.6	38	11.2	14	4.1
5	Community and family counselling should be promoted	294	87	22	6.5	22	6.5
6	Corruption eradication	300	88.7	30	8.9	8	2.4
7	Negotiation and mediation will yield more positive results	236	69.8	60	11.8	42	12.4
8	Religious tolerance and checking the activities of religious extremists	280	82.8	20	5.9	38	11.2
9	Appealing to aggrieved groups	244	72.3	58	17	36	10.7
10	State police should be established	202	59.8	86	25.4	50	14.8
11	Government should dialogue with aggrieved groups	276	81.7	34	10	28	8.3
12	Improved policing	284	84	34	10	20	5.9
13	Use of force by government	96	28.4	202	59.8	40	11.8
14	Free and fair election	304	89.9	26	7.7	8	2.4
15	Civic, moral instructions and peace education should be compulsorily taught in all schools	202	59.8	86	25.4	50	14.8
16	Improved living condition	296	87.6	32	9.5	10	3.0
17	Counselling services should be made available in all schools	310	91.7	12	3.6	16	4.7

It is crystal clear from the results in table 3 that, nearly, all the responses show that all the items in the table can curb/ameliorate Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria. Be that as it may, all the respondents openly abhorred "the use of force by government" as an item. This was the lowest of all responses (184 = 59.8%), while only a meagre response (28.4%); i.e only 96 respondents out of the 338 gave credence to the item possibly out of lack of understanding.

Test of Null Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the perceived causes of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy on the basis of gender in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

Table 4: The Z-test comparison of respondents' assessment of the causes of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

Gender	N	mean	SD	df	Z _{cal}	Z _{crit}
Male	186	76.03	12.30	168	1.89	1.95
Female	152	77.91	12.93			

Table 4 revealed that the calculated Z-value of 1.89 is less than the critical Z-value of 1.95. This result showed that the null hypothesis 1 has been accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the perceived causes of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy on the basis of Religion in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria.

Table 5: Z-test of difference in the perception of Christians and Muslims on the causes of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria.

Religion	N	mean	SD	df	Z _{cal}	Z _{crit}
Christians	286	76.37	14.06	168	0.57	1.95
Muslims	52	76.95	12.17			

The results in table 5 showed that the calculated Z-value of 0.57 is less than the critical Z-value of 1.95 showing that the null hypothesis 2 of no significant difference is accepted. That is, there is no significant difference in the perceived causes of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy between the respondents who are Christians and Muslims.

3. Discussion

The perceived causes and effects of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy were studied in this research work. It was obvious from the results that nearly all the items that caused Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy were positively perceived by the respondents. Be that as it may, the items rated high as the major causes of these trio evils in the Niger Delta Regions on Nigeria include unemployment, poverty, corruption, bad governance and slow or casual approach of government to sensitive issues in Nigeria. In fact, the issues of unemployment and poverty were corroborated by Chukwuemeka and Aghara (2007) study. In addition to this, the study of Mutiba (2011) gave credence and support to the items of lack of good governance, unemployment, corrupt practices and poverty as excruciating factors responsible for Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in Nigeria. From this study, it was revealed that further causes of these ills are youthful

exuberance, marginal services in schools, environmental degradation, tribal and or sectional loyalty among Nigerians, inadequate moral instructions in schools, religious intolerance, election rigging, and get-rich-quick-syndrome. Again, it was crystal clear that there was no significant difference in the perceived causes of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy between male and female respondents in the study. It was possibly so because these respondents were familiar with the different factors and events that occasioned these youths' mischief. In the same vein, the Christians and Muslims respondents were in agreement on the responsible reasons why these young ones take to these ills. The results actually revealed that the major effects of these trio evils are relocation of citizens to their tribal/ethnic environs, political instability, breakup of the nation, economic stagnation, war and exodus of foreigners from the country. From the study, the followings are some panaceas for the trio evils of these youths; teaching civic, moral and peace education, free and fair elections, transparent leadership and governance and the need to be positive and rational in thinking. Furthermore, poverty and corruption eradication and improved living styles are possible ways of ameliorating these ills from the society (Oyadeyi, 2012). Besides, dialogue, appeal and negotiation will help to a great deal in resolving the menace in question. Lastly, improved policing and or state police establishment would help the situation further. Be that as it may, the use of force to resolve the issues was not recommended at all from the results of the study.

Implication for Counselling

The youths with this trio-evils need professional counsellors to be able to overcome. These professionals must take the bull by the horn and save Nigeria from collapse due to the evils of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy.

Therefore, family and community counselling centres should be set up in the Niger Delta Regions, so as, to avert these evils. Above all, the mother body of the counsellors (CASSON) should put up bills to enable the government to empower them to reach out to these Restive, Terrorist and Militant groups in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria for the interest of political and economic peace.

4. Recommendations

- The federal government should take positive steps toward addressing poverty in the country, honestly.
- Steps should be taken to ameliorate the issues of high prices of essential commodities such as electricity bills, fuel pump prices, rents, housing problem, etc.
- Counselling services should be made available to youths in schools and out of schools.
- Casson in collaboration with the government should promote family and community counselling.
- For national peace and cohesion, the following services should be made available:
 - 1) Undertaking leadership training for youths from different religions, backgrounds, faith and ethnicities should be addressed.
 - 2) Organising short-term residential camps for our Restive youths, Terrorists and Militants.
 - 3) For national integration, multicultural activities should be organised.
 - 4) Promoting inter-state youths programmes like football, athletics, etc

- 5) Symposia and seminars on national integration should be organised.
- For peace and orderliness to reign in Nigeria, job creation must be given a priority for our idled millions of youths.
 - Churches, Mosques and religious bodies should admonish their followers to preach peace which is their onerous goal.
 - Our school curriculum at all levels should imbibe moral and peace education in their syllabi for our youths to be reformed.
 - The national anthem and pledge should not be recited and sang for singing sake. Their messages should be internalized and practiced in our daily lives, especially by the youths.
 - Finally, our complex and heterogeneous societies and ethnicities, peaceful co-existence should be practiced by our teeming youths to foster unity in the country.

5. Conclusion

The causes of Youth Restiveness, Terrorism and Militancy in the Niger Delta Areas of Nigeria have been unfolded by this study from the perceptions of the undergraduates of the Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State. All these were caused by the actions and inactions of the governments, individuals and groups in governance. The impending doom is the imminent collapse of the country's economies, politics and social wellbeing of Nigeria. The way out is to admonish all well-meaning Nigerians (Youths and government) to embrace peace and harmony, while those in power should urgently address the necessary solutions recommended in the study.

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